

The Design of English Vocabulary Learning Application

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Abstract- This research is underlain by the low of interest and ability of elementary school students in Kupang in mastering English vocabulary, a case study of the INPRES Liliba State Elementary School, Oebobo District, Kupang City, East Nusa Tenggara. The research objective is an Android-based English vocabulary learning design. English vocabulary learning applications can improve students mastery of English vocabulary, increase students motivation and interest in learning vocabulary, practice student-centered learning, trigger student creativity, effectiveness, build student independence in learning vocabulary, and create the teaching and learning process can be done whenever and wherever the students want to study. This thing is expected can change the mindset and culture of using mobile phones for elementary school students in Kupang so it can be used properly and efficiently for learning English vocabulary. The method of developing English vocabulary learning applications is the waterfall method which includes five stages, namely the identification of user needs about learning English vocabulary, analysis, designing, implementation, and testing.

Keywords: Learning applications, English vocabulary, elementary school, android, Kupang, waterfall

1. INTRODUCTION

Vocabulary is one of the important components in English. By mastering vocabulary well, it can be a basis for mastering English fluently. The learning method used in elementary schools in Kupang to deliver English material is the method of lecturing, discussion, question and answer, reading subject matter to students. It is difficult for students to master English because the learning is not interesting, students feel bored, students are not active, and it is difficult for students to understand the teacher's explanation because it

is theoretical. The rapid development and advancement of mobile phone technology which has become the main requirement for humans to communicate, shop, transact, convey information, get entertainment, play games, interact in social media, and learn so that mobile phones become high technology in today's digital era. This requires the world of education to apply learning technology using mobile phone which can accelerate the improvement of education quality, learning quality, and achievement of learning competencies. For building synergy between teachers and students in delivering and receiving of material, it needs innovation of the interactive and attractive learning models for students so it can motivate students' activeness to learn independently. The learning process, especially for students of elementary school, is not easy, because most of the characteristics of children cannot focus on learning time. Another difficulty of children in learning is the tendency of children's learning patterns to prefer to play. In addition, English is not the language that used daily both by children and parents, so children are not easy to comprehend English vocabularies that said by teacher in and pronounce them.

Study while playing using a mobile phone is very liked by children today, so it is necessary to think about using a mobile phone as a learning tool that is not limited by time and space. Through play, children are invited to explore, find and draw conclusions about the objects around them. Therefore become a new breakthrough in technologically advanced educational program, namely a learning model using a mobile phone to be utilized properly and efficiently for elementary school students in Kupang. A mobile phone that owned by student is not only used for social media services such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, playing

games, watching videos, reading messages, etc., but also can be an interesting medium for learning English and students can study wherever and whenever they want. Based on the description above, the research problem is how to design an English learning model using a mobile phone application so that it can improve vocabulary mastery for elementary school students in Kupang city.

The specific objectives of this study are

- a. Improving the ability and mastery of elementary school students in learning English vocabulary using a mobile phone application.
- b. Supporting English vocabulary learning activities at the elementary school level whenever and wherever students are, so that the teaching and learning process can be effective, efficient, and student-centered.
- c. Increasing students' motivation to learn independently, interactively, and attractively by using a mobile phone application.

The urgency of the research is to change the culture and mindset of elementary school students in Kupang in utilizing mobile phone devices so that they can be effective for learning English vocabulary which can accelerate mastering of English. The specification of the English vocabulary learning model using a mobile phone is to provide attractive and interactive learning services with animations, pictures, games, sounds and videos adapted to ages 5-12 years. The material in this application consists of learning letters A to Z, learning basic colors, learning numbers, learning animals, learning fruits, the human body, and learning objects around the child's environment.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning English at the basic level should emphasize the most basic and necessary elements of language, namely vocabulary, pronunciation, simple grammar, and simple conversation. Besides these language elements, one thing that English teachers should always remember is the importance of creating a comfortable situation and arousing interest and motivation in learning English (M. Yamin, 2017). The role of the media in the learning process can determine the success of education for elementary school students in Kupang. The choice of a learning method affects the type of learning media. The selection of learning media includes several things (Azhar Arsyad, 2011), namely (a) suitable to the objectives that will be achieved. Media are selected based on the instructional goals that have been set generally

referring to one or a combination of two or three cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains. This goal can be described in the form of tasks that must be done by students, such as memorizing, doing activities that involve physical activity or using principles such as cause and effect, doing tasks that involve understanding concepts or changing relationships, and doing tasks that involve thought at a high level. (b) Appropriate to support the content of lessons that are facts, concepts, principles, or generalizations. The media must be conformable and suitable with the needs of the learning task and the mental abilities of students. (c) Practical, flexible and be survive. Media that is expensive and takes a long time to produce is not a guarantee of the best media. (d) The skilled teacher to use it. This is one of the main criteria. The value and benefits are largely determined by the teacher who uses it. (e) Target group. Media that is effective for large groups is not necessarily effective for small groups. (f) Technical quality. The visual development of both images and photography must meet certain technical requirements.

The importance of learning vocabulary must be started early so that students do not have difficulty understanding and mastering English. To make it easier for learning English vocabulary for elementary school children, it is necessary to know the standard material that must be given for children, namely letters, animals, numbers, colors, my body, the surrounding environment, and introductions. Therefore it can be concluded that the learning material that must be given to children is only about vocabulary recognition of letter names, animal names, color types, names of body parts, and regarding the names of objects around the house and self-introduction using English. Kumar, et al (2013) state that the use of mobile phones is more increase which can changes the way of working and learning. This can facilitate students to access learning resources without present physically in the classroom. The advantages of using mobile learning are the enhancement of mobility which allows students to access learning content wherever they are, the efficiency of time and cost the teaching and learning process, learning media can be carried anywhere, and students can interact with teachers or classmates (Santosh 2013).

Mingsep and Bonifasia (2020) explain that learning mathematics using the smart school mobile application is a student-centered learning model. The development of digital technology has an impact on improving the

quality of learning and achieving competence. The Android-based smart school mobile application provides interactive and interesting mathematics learning material which includes text, audio / video, and evaluation.

3. METHOD

The development of mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning application software uses the waterfall method which includes five stages, namely: (1) identification of user needs, (2) analysis, (3) design, (4) implementation, and (5) testing. The following picture shows the method of developing English vocabulary learning applications.

- a. Identify user needs. The first step of the research was to make observations and interview with the elementary school of Impres Liliba State, Oebobo District, Kupang City, East Nusa Tenggara to collect data and information about the English vocabulary learning system.
- b. Analysis. The analysis stage is the decomposition of the English vocabulary learning system as a whole into simpler parts with the aim of identifying and evaluating problems, opportunities, obstacles that occur, and the needs of the Impres Liliba Public Elementary School to implement an English-based vocabulary learning system. mobile phone. At this stage the data / information analysis results of the identification of user needs are carried out to get a complete understanding of the learning processes. At this stage, the requirements of the mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning system have been determined.
- c. Design. The stage of translating the results of the analysis into a form that is easily understood by users and programmers. Based on the results of the analysis of user needs, a modeling design is carried out to capture and explain all user needs and the transformation of the analysis results into a user interface design for a mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning application system.
- d. Implementation. Implementation is the stage for creating a mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning application program.
- e. Testing. Testing the mobile phone-based English vocabulary learning application, is the testing phase of the application operation that has been made, correcting errors and changes to the application. The test will be carried out on students of the Impres Liliba Elementary School in Kupang City.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. English Vocabulary Application Design.

The design of the Android-based English vocabulary learning application is an application that introduces vocabulary learning to the Liliba Impress elementary school students which are divided into seven material menus, namely learning the letters AZ, numbers, colors, fruits, animals, human bodies, and environmental objects. in class. Analysis of functional and operational requirements of the mobile vocabulary english application is modeled using UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagrams which include use case diagrams and activity diagrams. Use case diagrams are part of the functionality of the system which will describe the interaction between actors (students) and the system to be built. The interaction between students as application users and the system includes seven processes, namely learning letters, numbers, human body parts, surrounding objects, colors, fruits, and learning about animals. Activity diagrams describe the work flow or processes that occur in the mobile vocabulary English application system. Figure 1 shows the use case diagram of the English mobile vocabulary application and Figure 2 shows the activity diagram of the English mobile vocabulary application.

Figure 1. Use Case Diagram of English Vocabulary Applications

Figure 2. Sequence Diagram of English Vocabulary Applications

Figure 3. Menu Structure of English Vocabulary Applications

4.2. Implementation of English Vocabulary Learning Applications

The implementation of the mobile vocabulary learning application can improve the ability of English vocabulary for elementary school students and change the way students learn effectively and efficiently. This can facilitate students to access learning resources without the need to be physically present in the classroom. The advantages of using English vocabulary learning applications are increased mobility that allows students to access learning content anywhere, time and cost efficiency for the teaching and learning process, learning media is easy to carry anywhere, and students can interact with teachers or classmates. The menu structure of the English mobile vocabulary application is shown in Figure 3. The mobile vocabulary learning application interface is shown in Figure 4, Figure 5, and Figure 6.

Figure 4. Application Start View

Figure 5. Display of Main Menu

Figure 6. Video Live Streaming

Figure 7. Lesson module

4.3. Discussion

The results of research on the ability of elementary school students for the subject matter of letters, numbers, colors, fruits, animals, human bodies, and environmental objects before using the English vocabulary application are as follows:

1. The average score of Inpres Liliba primary school students based on the pre test given by the research team is low, namely 61. This score does not meet the minimum passing competency standards.
2. The low interest of Inpres Liliba elementary school students in learning English vocabulary and difficulty in focusing on learning and capturing what the teacher / research team said.
3. Inpres Liliba elementary school children tend to prefer to play rather than study, therefore a mobile phone application is needed as a learning aid that students can use to play and learn anytime and anywhere because it is easy to carry everywhere.

The process of learning English for vocabulary subject matter, especially for elementary school children, Inpres Liliba is not easy, because most of the characteristics of children cannot focus on learning time. Another difficulty of children in learning is due to the tendency of children's learning patterns to prefer to play. In addition, English is not the language used daily by children and parents, so children are not used to catching what the teacher is saying and pronouncing the pronunciation in English. Learning while playing using a mobile phone is very popular with children today so it is necessary to think about using a mobile phone as a learning tool that is not limited by time and space. Through play, children are invited to explore, find and draw conclusions about learning English vocabulary. This is a new breakthrough with advanced technology, namely a learning model using a mobile phone so that it can be utilized properly and effectively for students of the Inpres Liliba elementary school in Kupang, Indonesia. Learning using a mobile phone or smartphone owned by each student is not only used for social media services (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter), playing games, watching videos, reading messages, etc. but can be a medium for learning English vocabulary. interesting and students can study wherever and whenever they want.

5. CONCLUSION

- a. The design of the English vocabulary learning application is modeled in the form of a UML (Unified Modeling Language) diagram which includes use case diagrams and activity diagrams. Use case diagrams explain the interaction between students (actors) and the English vocabulary learning application. The interaction between students as application users with the English vocabulary learning application includes seven processes, namely learning letters, numbers, human body parts, surrounding objects, colors, fruits, and learning about animals. Activity diagrams describe the work flow or processes that occur in the mobile vocabulary English application system.
- b. The application of learning English vocabulary can increase students' motivation and interest in learning English vocabulary, student-centered learning, triggering student creativity, effectiveness, building student independence in learning vocabulary, and the teaching and learning process can be done whenever and wherever students want to learn.

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